

Systematic Review Methods in Environmental Health: a critical interpretive synthesis to inform the evolution of systematic review guidance

Authors

Emily Senerth (a, b), Neha Tangri (a), Lori Krammer (c), Volf Gaby (d), Paul Whaley (b, e), Giffe Johnson (f), Katya Tsaïoun (b), Rebecca L. Morgan (a, d, g)

Affiliations

- (a) Evidence Foundation
- (b) EBTC at Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health
- (c) George Washington University
- (d) McMaster University
- (e) Lancaster University
- (f) National Council for Air and Stream Improvement (NCASI)
- (g) Case Western Reserve University

Corresponding author: Rebecca L. Morgan (rlm180@case.edu)

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Abstract

Background: Systematic reviews are generally regarded as the most reliable and rigorous approach to evidence synthesis. Within the field of environmental health, systematic review methods are used to identify relationships between exposures, exposure mitigation interventions, and health outcomes. However, there are multiple strategies for conducting systematic reviews of exposures. This review aims to provide a comprehensive assessment of current systematic review frameworks, and to characterize similarities and differences between systematic review approaches from across the field of environmental health.

Methods: We performed an English-language search of MEDLINE via PubMed, EMBASE, and Cochrane databases from January 1, 2013, through March 30, 2023 for systematic review frameworks applied to environmental health research questions. Additionally, we searched 35 organizational websites and references of included studies to identify additional frameworks outside of the peer-reviewed literature. For the critical interpretive synthesis, we purposively sampled and extracted data from frameworks that contributed new information to at least one of the following themes grounded in the PRISMA framework: research question, protocol, search strategy, study selection, data extraction, data synthesis, risk of bias assessment, overall certainty assessment, and reporting findings. Frameworks also addressed disclosure of funding sources and conflict of interest, feasibility considerations, limitations, and directions for future research.

Results: From 3,417 studies identified through the database search, we included 5 published frameworks. We included another 16 frameworks identified from organizational websites and citation searching; 14 frameworks were included in our purposive sample. Most frameworks (n = 10) originated from North America. Five frameworks addressed all of our predefined themes; all frameworks addressed at least 6 of the 9 themes. Additionally, 9 frameworks described an approach to integrating epidemiologic data with information from animal or in vitro studies. Although we observed variability in whether or how thoroughly frameworks addressed each of the themes, different approaches did not contradict each other within a theme. Rather, frameworks differed in the degree of methodological rigor that was suggested or recommended.

Conclusion: This systematic review and critical interpretive synthesis provide a comprehensive overview of systematic review approaches in environmental health, proposing necessary domains to guide systematic reviews in environmental health. Operational guidance complements the proposed framework domains. Findings may be useful to researchers who are selecting an approach for their review or developing resources to facilitate the uptake of systematic methods for reviews of environmental exposures.

Introduction

High-quality systematic reviews are critical for the transparent, reproducible, and data-driven evaluation of scientific research.^{1,2} According to the Cochrane Handbook, “systematic reviews seek to collate evidence that fits pre-specified eligibility criteria in order to answer a specific research question. They aim to minimize bias by using explicit, systematic methods documented in advance with a protocol.”¹ The emergence of systematic review (SR) methodologies marked a pivotal shift away from more subjective approaches to evidence synthesis and addressed significant challenges to the translation of research findings into trustworthy policies and interventions. These challenges include delays in the integration of scientific discoveries into existing practices, delays in the identification of important harms or risks to human health, duplication of efforts, and lack of reproducibility. Observing the benefits of systematic review methods in other contexts, scientists, researchers, and policymakers began to explore whether these methods could be applied to environmental health (EH). Early efforts focused on adopting or adapting methodologies that were initially developed to address questions about clinical interventions using epidemiological data to suit the unique environmental health research landscape.³ These efforts are the foundation for rigorous and comprehensive approaches to evaluation of evidence that have increasingly become central to decision-making in the field.

The impact of systematic review approaches on environmental health has been profound.⁴⁻⁹ Policymakers, regulatory agencies, and public health officials now rely on these methods to make informed decisions about exposure limits, risk management strategies, and mitigation interventions.¹⁰ The rigorous evaluation of evidence certainty, coupled with the transparent reporting of findings, confers credibility on the recommendations that result from systematic reviews, thereby influencing policy formulation and public discourse.¹¹

As the field of environmental health continues to evolve, systematic review approaches are poised to undergo further advancements.¹¹ Methodological innovations, including the integration of machine learning and advanced data analytics, promise to increase efficiencies throughout the review process while maintaining robustness. Furthermore, the influence of interdisciplinary collaboration will likely be ongoing. Environmental health research often intersects with other fields such as epidemiology, toxicology, and even social sciences. Collaborative efforts that combine data from multiple disciplines may become increasingly relevant in our efforts to grapple with the complex pathway from environmental exposure to health outcome.

Meanwhile, deserved emphasis on the positive impact of systematic review methods has led to a proliferation of strategies for conducting systematic reviews in environmental health. These approaches aim to align human, infrastructure, and technological resources with appropriately rigorous methods to minimize waste and improve efficiency.^{12–14} A comprehensive assessment of current frameworks and methodologies will provide valuable insight into similarities, differences, and key tradeoffs between systematic review approaches across the field of environmental health research. In addition to resource constraints, these frameworks may also provide insight into perceived barriers to adoption of systematic review methods. This project aims to collect and describe current systematic review approaches in environmental health research and identify knowledge gaps to inform future research.

Methods

We performed a systematic review and critical interpretive synthesis to answer the research question: what approaches or frameworks are being used to conduct systematic reviews in the field of environmental health? We followed the standards described in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 statement and registered the review protocol in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) database (CRD42023416425).¹⁵ First, the research team conducted a search of the peer-reviewed and gray literature to identify available documentation of systematic review methods that are being applied or are intended for application in environmental health. Second, the team extracted information about the identified methods and their developers. Third, we used the PRISMA 2020 standards as a foundation to compare and contrast different approaches. Finally, we summarized additional feasibility considerations described by framework developers.

Terminology

Throughout this project, we have used terminology to distinguish various levels of granularity in theories and concepts that apply to the conduct of systematic reviews. Often, these terms describe overlapping or nested elements, which may be confusing. Definitions for frequently used terms are as follows, from the broadest to the most specific:

- *Systematic review approach*: an over-arching strategy or theory for conducting a systematic review; may encompass both frameworks and methods
- *Framework*: an organized structure comprised of standardized elements for conducting a systematic review; may encompass methods, domains, and themes as defined below

- *Methodology*: a research procedure for one or several components of a systematic review (e.g., inverse-variance is a method for performing meta-analysis)
- *Domain*: a main component of the PRISMA 2020 checklist; also called “items” by PRISMA (e.g., provide an explicit statement of the research question)
- *Theme*: concepts or constructs that are contained within each domain or item (e.g., use PICO or PECO framework to format the research question)

Data sources and search strategy

In consultation with an information specialist, we developed and utilized a database search strategy to identify published reports of frameworks used to guide the conduct of systematic reviews to assess questions about the human health effects of environmental exposures, the magnitude of disease burden related to environmental exposures, and the benefits and harms of mitigation efforts aimed at environmental exposures. The research team conducted a search of electronic bibliographic databases Cochrane, Embase, and MEDLINE via PubMed in March 2023. The full search strategy is available as Supplement A. The search was restricted to studies published in the English language within the last ten years (January 2013 - March 2023). This date restriction was intended to minimize the detection of duplicate or obsolete frameworks and to facilitate collection of current approaches.

In addition to the electronic database search, the team performed a hand search of government, organizational, and other websites. We anticipated that many important sources on this topic would not be available as publications and calibrated the gray literature search accordingly. Our hand search included targeted browsing of websites of agencies or organizations that are engaged in research on the health effects of environmental exposures or regulation of these exposures, advanced google searching of the aforementioned websites, and a search of gray literature databases including the Federal Register and GovInfo. This search also included review of text and reference lists of full text published reports during study selection to identify additional eligible documents. The gray literature search strategy is provided in Supplement B.

Study selection

We imported database search results to Covidence (Covidence systematic review software, Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia. Available at www.covidence.org) to identify duplicates and screen titles, abstracts, and full texts. Throughout all phases of study selection,

two researchers performed screening independently and in duplicate (ES, NT, LK, VG), and resolved any disagreements through discussion or by consulting a third reviewer (ES).

We included published or public reports of frameworks, manuals, methods, and protocols detailing systematic review methods used for reviews of environmental health topics. If we found multiple versions of the same framework, we included the most recent iteration of each framework and noted any previous iterations. Reports were excluded if they did not present a framework or approach to conducting systematic reviews, described methods or approaches for scoping reviews, presented a tool for risk of bias assessment without addressing other components of a systematic review, were not relevant to environmental health, or if the full text of the report was not available (Figure 1). Lists of the inclusion and exclusion criteria are provided in Supplement C.

Data extraction and sampling

We designed and piloted a standardized data extraction form to collect information about the characteristics of included reports (date published or made public, individual or organizational developer, funding sources, geographic location) and frameworks (intended application, framework components, reporting standards, and feasibility considerations). Data was extracted into Google Sheets by one researcher and all data were reviewed by a second researcher. Disagreements were resolved through discussion or by consulting a third reviewer. The data extraction template is provided in Supplement D.

We selected the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement as a foundation for our approach to data collection and sampling. PRISMA 2020 provides a minimum set of items for reporting systematic review methods: the review rationale and objectives, eligibility criteria, information sources, search strategy, selection process, data collection process, data items, conducting and reporting risk of bias assessment, synthesis methods, certainty assessment, and reporting of methods, results, and other information such as protocol registration, competing interests, and funding sources. We selected PRISMA 2020 because of its credibility, applicability across different fields of research, and because of its stated goal to present basic reporting standards for systematic reviews. PRISMA has been endorsed by the Cochrane Collaboration and over 100 scientific journals that review and publish systematic reviews.¹⁶ Additionally, PRISMA is the reporting guideline for systematic reviews adopted by the EQUATOR Network (Enhancing the QUALity and Transparency of Health Care Research).¹⁷

We purposively sampled eligible frameworks until we achieved saturation of themes. Frameworks were sampled if they contributed new information to any of the PRISMA domains or if they introduced a new domain. If a framework self-identified as derivative of another approach without contributing new information, we sampled only the original framework. If the relationship between frameworks was unclear, we reached out to the developer to clarify.

Data synthesis

We summarized characteristics of included reports and frameworks using descriptive statistics, including counts of characteristics such as geographic region and proportions of characteristics within the whole sample. This provides insight into the representativeness or generalizability of our sample. We reported framework characteristics using tabulation.

We used narrative synthesis to analyze components of the included frameworks in relation to the reporting domains of our foundational framework, the PRISMA 2020 statement: research question, protocol, search strategy, study selection, data extraction, data synthesis methods, risk of bias assessment, certainty assessment, and reporting results.¹⁵ Initially we used an inductive approach to assess whether or not a framework component was related to each PRISMA domain, then summarized the related elements of the frameworks under each domain, and finally summarized granular considerations or suggestions for operationalizing each domain.¹⁸ Our synthesis progressed from the broadest element of each framework to the narrowest. We then examined the similarities and differences between approaches, noting when multiple frameworks addressed the same concept in a similar way. We also noted any exceptions to common approaches described in our sample. Decisions to separate or consolidate framework components, and to relate framework components to PRISMA domains were proposed by one researcher (ES) and agreed upon by the full team.

Results

Search results

Our database search identified 3,417 papers, complemented by an additional 35 reports sourced through a manual search of unpublished sources, and another 47 sources pulled from citation exploration (Figure 1). Duplicate results ($n = 311$) were removed before study selection was performed. We screened 3,106 titles and abstracts of published records and excluded 3,059 from further consideration. Of the 47 full texts assessed for eligibility, 42 were excluded

and one full text was not retrieved for screening because the full publication was not available (Supplement D). Of the 82 reports identified from our gray literature search, 66 were excluded and one full text was not retrieved for screening because the full publication was not available. The most common reason for exclusion was that a report did not present a framework or approach for the conduct of systematic reviews (n = 62 across database and gray literature combined). Other reasons for exclusion are: the report addressed scoping review methods (n = 3), the report presented a tool for risk of bias assessment (n = 2) or meta-analysis (n = 2), multiple iterations of the same framework (n = 18), older iterations of eligible frameworks (n = 6) or that the framework was not relevant for application to environmental health (n = 8). After the study selection process, 21 frameworks were eligible for inclusion and 14 were ultimately included in our purposive sample. All reviewers unanimously agreed on decisions to include or exclude frameworks during study selection. Following study selection, discussions between reviewers during data extraction clarified interpretation of sampled frameworks and the relationship of concepts presented to PRISMA domains.

Description of framework characteristics

Selected frameworks include the Center for Environmental Evidence (CEE) Guidelines for Systematic Review and Evidence Synthesis in Environmental Management, the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) Office of Research and Development (ORD) Staff Handbook for Developing Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS) Assessments, European Food Safety Association's Guidance on Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making, the Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT) Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) Preamble to Monographs on the Identification of Carcinogenic Hazards to Humans, and the Navigation Guide Systematic Review Methodology.^{3,19–23} Most frameworks we sampled were developed to address environmental health topics such as chemical and food safety (Table 1). However, we also included several frameworks that were not specific to environmental health, but were referenced as relevant approaches to systematic reviews of environmental exposures: Extending the PRISMA statement to equity-focused systematic reviews (PRISMA-E), and Realist And MEta-narrative Evidence Syntheses: Evolving Standards (RAMESES) publication standards for meta-narrative reviews.^{24,25} These frameworks exemplify the interdisciplinary crossover of SR approaches that were originally developed for clinical or social science questions into the field of environmental health.

The geographic distribution of frameworks in our sample is weighted towards North America, with Canada representing the highest proportion at 42.9%, closely followed by the USA at 28.6%. Europe, Asia, and Australia contributed 14.2%, 7.1%, and 7.1% of the reports, respectively. The earliest frameworks in our sample were published or made public from 2013-2015 (28.6%). An equal proportion of frameworks (also 28.6%) were released from 2022-2023. The relatively consistent rate of framework reports over the 10-year period we examined reflects ongoing interest in SR approaches for environmental health. None of the frameworks in our sample underwent a formal validation process, with 35.7% acknowledging this as a limitation or opportunity for future research (Tables 1 & 2).

Relationship to PRISMA 2020

We observed substantial overlap between the frameworks in our sample and our foundational framework, PRISMA 2020. All frameworks addressed at least 6 of the 9 PRISMA domains. Additionally, 9 frameworks described an approach to integrating epidemiologic data with information from animal or in vitro studies. In particular, the domains around developing a search strategy and performing study selection were universally addressed. Formulating a research question, developing a protocol, approaches to data synthesis, and risk of bias and certainty assessment were also commonly addressed. Data extraction and reporting results received relatively less attention but were still mentioned by a majority of frameworks (Table 3). Within each domain, we noted instances of commonality and variability in approaches as follows:

Research Question

Most frameworks (n = 13, 93%) described the formulation of a specific and answerable research question as an essential step for conducting a systematic review (Table 3).^{3,15,19–22,24–29} Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome (PICO) and Population, Exposure, Comparison, Outcome (PECO) format were mentioned as question structures.³⁰ We noted some variability in the stakeholders who may be involved in question formulation, with a single framework proposing that both research funders and end users should be involved.²⁵

Protocol

Pre-specifying the review methods in a protocol was also mentioned by most frameworks (n = 13, 93%).^{3,15,19–22,24–29} Multiple approaches to protocol development were referenced, including

PRISMA for systematic review protocols (PRISMA-P), the Cochrane Handbook, and the PROCEED database format.^{1,31,32} Frameworks also described several platforms for publishing or publicly posting an SR protocol, including: the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO), the PROCEED database, the Collaborative Approach to Meta-Analysis and Review of Animal Data from Experimental Studies (CAMARADES) platform, Zenodo, and the Center for Open Science OSF Registry.^{32–36}

Literature Search Strategy

All frameworks (n = 14) mentioned search strategy development with the aim of identifying all relevant data. In this section, frameworks described calibration of the search strategy to balance the detection of pertinent studies with capacity to perform subsequent screening. Five frameworks (36%) recommended engaging a librarian or information specialist in this stage of the systematic review.^{19,20,23,26,29} In addition to major scientific databases such as MEDLINE, EH researchers may also consider topically specialized resources such as the Systematic Review Centre for Laboratory Animal Experimentation (SYRCLE) and Toxline.^{22,26} Finally, most of the frameworks in our sample (n = 11, 79%) included a gray literature search as part of a comprehensive search strategy.^{3,15,19–24,26,29,37}

Study Selection

All frameworks (n = 14) described study selection as an essential step of conducting a systematic review, separating relevant sources from irrelevant using well-defined inclusion and exclusion (eligibility) criteria. Study selection is commonly performed in duplicate, with discussion between screeners, the involvement of a third reviewer, or both used to resolve disagreements. PRISMA 2020 provides the most detailed guidance for documenting the study selection process.¹⁵

Data Extraction

Eleven frameworks (79%) also mentioned data extraction. Multiple reviewers may also be involved in this step to ensure accuracy, either extracting in duplicate or extraction performed by one reviewer and reviewed by a second. Two frameworks introduced the option of utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) to increase efficiency in both the study selection and data extraction steps.^{20,29}

Data Synthesis Methods

Most frameworks in our sample provided some guidance for selecting appropriate methods of quantitative data synthesis (n = 13, 93%).^{15,19,20,22–26,37} Two frameworks (14%) addressed approaches to qualitative synthesis, including thematic analysis, narrative summary, qualitative aggregation, and realist synthesis.^{25,28} Frameworks that incorporated approaches for integrating non-human evidence also identified data synthesis as a junction when evidence from multiple sources may be integrated into a single evidence profile.^{3,20–22,26,27}

Risk of Bias Assessment

Most frameworks (n = 13, 93%) indicated that some type of study-level risk of bias assessment, or appraisal of internal validity, should be performed as part of a systematic review. However, accommodating the diverse range of study designs found in environmental health research can introduce complexity. Frameworks suggested the use of tailored risk of bias assessment tools that have been developed to address the unique challenges posed by observational and exposure data, such as ROBINS-I or ROBINS-E.^{38,39} Other options mentioned for non-randomized studies are the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS), the Downs and Black checklist, the OHAT RoB Tool, and the National Institute on Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) Office of the Report on Carcinogens (ORoC) Tool.^{22,40–42} When randomized evidence is available, even from randomized wildlife populations, seven frameworks (50%) indicated that the Cochrane Risk of Bias (RoB) 2.0 tool is applicable.^{3,20,22,26–29,37} Two frameworks introduced bespoke risk of bias tools.^{19,22} Frameworks recognized that selection of a tool is highly specific to both the study design and subject matter; it may be necessary to use multiple tools within a single systematic review, especially when pulling data from multiple evidence streams. In situations where multiple reviewers disagree on a judgment about potential bias, most frameworks suggested a consensus-based approach to reach agreement between reviewers. However, one framework suggested selecting the most conservative judgment (assuming the highest risk of bias) from among differing assessments.²⁰

Certainty Assessment

Broadly, approaches to certainty assessment described in our sample (n = 13, 93%) can be summarized in three categories: frameworks that adopted the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) approach directly, those that recommended some modification of GRADE, and frameworks that derive another approach to

certainty assessment from the Bradford Hill criteria.⁴³ Three frameworks did not specify an approach to certainty assessment, but did mention it as a component of SR in environmental health.^{19,21,25} The GRADE approach to overall certainty assessment is described in detail elsewhere.^{44–46} Modifications to GRADE proposed by frameworks in our sample include: replacing the “inconsistency” domain with “unexplained inconsistency,” addition of domains “consistency,” “confidence,” and “coherence,” and omission of the domains “indirectness,” “imprecision,” “publication bias,” “dose-response gradient,” and “opposing residual confounding.”^{20,22} These are detailed in Table 5.

Approaches to describing the overall certainty in the evidence varied between frameworks that provided specific guidance for doing so (n = 8, 57%). The most common structure involves four categories: high, moderate (or medium), low, and very low certainty.^{15,22,26} A three-category structure was also described in multiple frameworks: high, medium, and low certainty.^{27,29} Another three frameworks described terminology that was unique to them, described in Table 5.^{3,20,23}

Reporting Results

Six frameworks (43%) recommended that SR results be reported in a format selected by the researchers, including monographs, meeting reports, or peer-reviewed articles.^{3,20–22,25,37} Another six frameworks (43%) outlined specific elements of the review that should be included in a report of the results.^{15,19,23,24,26,28} The RepOrting standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses in environmental research (ROSES) and Systematic Review Centre for Laboratory Animal Experimentation (SYRCLE) checklist were mentioned as reporting standards for SRs in EH.^{47,48} A comprehensive list of reporting elements described in our sample is as follows, with individual framework approaches detailed in Table 5: research question, applicability, justification of search limitations, search terms, PICO question, analysis/synthesis approach, individual study results, results of synthesis or meta-analysis, certainty of evidence, discussion of limitations and implications of the results for practice and policy.

Feasibility considerations

Frameworks also mentioned operational elements of conducting a systematic review, such as disclosure of funding sources for the review and personnel required to complete the recommended SR processes (Table 6). Disclosure of potential financial and intellectual conflicts of interest (COI) emerged as a consistent theme, with most frameworks (n = 10, 71%)

stipulating the collection of disclosure information. Personnel requirements were mostly not specified but can be inferred from steps such as study selection, where at least two reviewers are strongly encouraged. Other technical and feasibility considerations include: approaches to prioritizing questions to be answered by a systematic review, outlining the scope of questions that can be answered with a systematic review vs. those that cannot, the use of SRs to validate new approach methodologies (NAMs), qualifications for review team members, and the expected time frame to complete the steps outlined in the framework (Table 6).

Additionally, several frameworks (n = 7, 50%) described challenges and limitations associated with framework development and implementation (Table 6). A common theme from this sample is the difficulty in striking an appropriate balance so that a framework is both generalizable across different topics and specific enough to facilitate consistent operationalization. Along these lines, the possibility of varied interpretations of terminology and adherence to framework processes by framework users were also identified as limitations. Finally, framework developers recognized that approaches may continue to evolve in concert with other methodological advancements. This is also reflected in the multiple iterations we found for some of the frameworks during our search (Table 1).

Distinct systematic review considerations in environmental health

This review also aimed to identify elements in our sampled frameworks that are not addressed by PRISMA 2020. Differences between clinical or public health systematic review approaches and those formulated for environmental health often stem from the integration of mechanistic data, animal data, and observational data into assessments of environmental exposures. In some cases, such as establishing carcinogenicity, once an effect is observed in a non-human population it may be unethical to conduct further research in humans.²³ In other situations, such as establishing the effect of potentially harmful noise levels, it would be unreasonable to intentionally expose a population, but observational data from an incidentally exposed population may be available. While systematic reviews of clinical interventions may exclude these types of evidence because experimental studies in humans are available, environmental health researchers have developed approaches to collect, assess, and combine evidence from multiple different “streams” (Table 5). The frameworks in our sample illustrate the importance of observational, animal, and in vitro evidence to answering questions about environmental exposures.

When formulating a research question, Vandenberg et. al. suggest the development of a separate PECO question for each evidence stream, including non-animal, laboratory animal, wildlife, and human data.²⁹ Several frameworks described approaches for identifying, selecting, and synthesizing human, animal, and mechanistic evidence in parallel streams, which are then considered together as a single body of evidence.^{3,20–22,26,27} For example, evidence from non-human sources may be used to establish the consistency or biological plausibility of an effect. Importantly, frameworks that addressed this issue were unanimous in suggesting that researchers perform a separate risk of bias and/or certainty assessment of each evidence stream.^{3,20–23,26,27,29}

Discussion

The primary difference between PRISMA 2020, a “gold standard” approach to SRs of health-related interventions, and our sample of frameworks is the consideration of a broader scope of study designs, populations, and settings. Most of the PRISMA domains were addressed by most of our sampled frameworks for environmental health systematic reviews, with a few gaps as noted above. We also observed variability in the tactics and tools that were proposed to operationalize the key domains to conduct a systematic review.

Approaches to risk of bias assessment and overall certainty assessment highlight the most substantial differences between frameworks. We observed agreement about the importance of study-level risk of bias assessment among EH SR frameworks, although there were differences in the tools and domains used for this assessment. These differences are due in part to the selection of different tools that are appropriate for different study designs. They also reflect a lack of consensus around the key concepts to consider in RoB assessment in EH. Notably, the proportion of frameworks that suggest, recommend, or require RoB assessment reflects an emerging consensus on the importance of RoB compared to trends observed in the recent past.⁴⁹ Overall certainty assessment is not as consistently mentioned in our sample as study-level RoB assessment. However, approaches described between frameworks are broadly consistent, with most frameworks adopting the GRADE approach. The most common alternative to GRADE is the Bradford Hill criteria for causation. These approaches are conceptually similar, as GRADE considers each of the Bradford Hill criteria within its assessment domains.⁵⁰

In summary, we found substantial agreement between frameworks with some notable variability in the operationalization of SR domains across frameworks. This variability may stem from the context in which the framework is intended to be applied (e.g., a regulatory process vs.

academic research), or the tools and methods that were available and commonly used when the framework was developed. These variations also underscore the nuances of balancing methodological rigor with practical feasibility.

Strengths & Limitations

We employed a rigorous approach to data collection, conducting both a database search and exhaustive hand search of unpublished documents. This is reflected in the diversity of our purposive sample and the fact that we reached saturation of themes before extracting all eligible frameworks. However, this approach did not capture information outside of the published and gray literature. In particular, our sample reflects ideal practices in EH SR; the frameworks themselves recognize that there may be a gap between what is ideal and what is actually done in practice. Additionally, the use of a purposive sample means that this work does not represent an exhaustive inventory of SR approaches in EH. Finally, our analysis is grounded in a recognized and widely adopted approach to systematic review, the PRISMA 2020 statement. Although this framework was not originally developed to address environmental health SRs, we observed substantial alignment that supports the selection of this tool as a foundation. Judgments made by these researchers about the linkages between PRISMA and our sample are the result of our interpretations and may not be fully replicable.

Implications

This study extends an existing body of research to describe the landscape of systematic review methods within environmental health research, including approaches to the integration of multiple evidence streams.^{51,52} Our results may be useful to researchers who are interested in comparing and contrasting different systematic review approaches. We also aimed to provide a basis for further assessment of different approaches. Researchers may leverage these findings to select an approach that is suited to their goals, or to generate additional resources that facilitate the adoption of systematic review methods for evaluating environmental exposures. This work may also support standardization of approaches to SR and reduce research waste via the selection of appropriate tools and methods.

Future Research

Future research may include a survey or Delphi processes to elicit opinions on the applicability and utility of framework domains, discover additional domains that are not evident in written

material, characterize challenges related to feasibility and operationalization, forecast new opportunities for innovation, and assess the adequacy of current guidance on review methods in EH. Additionally, future research could explore approaches to the integration of mechanistic research in systematic reviews. The scope of this project did not include an assessment of the advantages or disadvantages of different frameworks, evaluation of adherence to published or public systematic review frameworks, or exhaustive exploration of the differences between frameworks based on their characteristics. These questions may be further explored by additional research. Finally, this study may inform the development of widely accepted best practices for systematic reviews in environmental health.

CRedit statement

ES: Data curation, investigation, methodology, project administration, writing - original draft preparation, writing - review and editing

NT: Investigation, writing - review and editing

LK: Investigation, writing - original draft preparation

VG: Investigation, writing - original draft preparation

PW: Conceptualization, methodology, writing - review and editing

GJ: Conceptualization, methodology, writing - review and editing

KT: Writing - review and editing

RLM: Conceptualization, methodology, supervision, writing - review and editing

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Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 diagram

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Table 1. Summary of included frameworks

Framework Characteristics	Total sample = 14 N (%)
Geographic Location	
North America	10 (71.4)
Europe	2 (14.2)
Asia	1 (7.1)
Australia	1 (7.1)
Topic Area	
Environmental Health (general)	3 (21.4)
Toxicology & Chemical Safety	7 (50.0)
Health Equity & Health Outcomes	2 (14.2)
Food & Feed Safety	1 (7.1)
Climate Change	1 (7.1)
Year (published/public)	
2022-2023	4 (28.6)
2020-2021	3 (21.4)
2018-2019	2 (14.2)
2016-2017	2 (14.2)
2010-2015	4 (28.6)
Validation of framework	
No	5 (35.7)
Not Reported	9 (64.3)

Table 2. Framework characteristics

Framework ID	Title	Version	Developing Organization or Developer Affiliation	Location	Funding Source	Topic Area	Evidence Type
CEE 2022	Guidelines for Systematic Review and Evidence Synthesis in Environmental Management	5.1	Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (CEE)	Europe	Not specified	Environmental management	Human
EFSA 2010	EFSA Guidance: Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making	1	European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)	Europe	Not specified	Food and feed safety	Human and non-human (animal data)
EPA 2022	Office of Research and Development (ORD) Staff Handbook for Developing Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS) Assessments	1	US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Office of Research and Development, Center for Public Health and Environmental Assessment	USA	Not specified	Hazard identification and dose-response analyses for chemicals found in the environment	Human and non-human (animal data)
Farhat 2022	Systematic Review in Evidence-Based Risk Assessment	1	McLaughlin Centre for Population Health Risk Assessment, University of Ottawa	Canada	Not specified	Chemical risk assessments, toxicology	Human, in vivo and in vitro
OHAT 2019	OHAT Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration	2	National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS), Division of the National Toxicology Program (NTP), Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT)	USA	US Department of Health & Human Services	Toxicology	Human and non-human (animal data)

Framework ID	Title	Version	Developing Organization or Developer Affiliation	Location	Funding Source	Topic Area	Evidence Type
Page 2021	The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews	2	School of Public Health and Preventive Medicine, Monash University, Melbourne, Australia	Australia	No direct funding	Health interventions, evaluating etiology, prevalence, or prognosis of health conditions	Human
Schaefer 2017	Guidelines for performing systematic reviews in the development of toxicity factors	1	Texas Commission on Environmental Quality (TCEQ)	USA	Not specified	Chemical toxicity factors	Human and non-human (animal data)
Shaffril 2020	Guidelines for developing a systematic literature review for studies related to climate change adaptation	1	Institute for Social Science Studies, Universiti Putra Malaysia	Asia	Ministry of Higher Education Malaysia under LRGS grant scheme	Climate change	Human
Vandenberg 2016	A proposed framework for the systematic review and integrated assessment (SYRINA) of endocrine disrupting chemicals	1	Swedish Foundation for Strategic Environmental Research "Mistra"	Europe	Swedish Foundation for Strategic Environmental Research "Mistra", NIEHS, Clarence Heller Foundation, Passport Foundation, Forsythia Foundation, US EPA STAR grants, Academy of Finland and Sigrid Juselius, Danish EPA, Canada Research Chairs program grant	Endocrine toxicology	Human, non-human (non-animal, animal, wildlife), and in vitro (laboratory animal)

Framework ID	Title	Version	Developing Organization or Developer Affiliation	Location	Funding Source	Topic Area	Evidence Type
Welch 2015	Extending the PRISMA statement to equity-focused systematic reviews (PRISMA-E 2012): explanation and elaboration	2	University of Ottawa	Canada	Canadian Institutes of Health Research and Rockefeller Foundation, University Research Chair	Health equity	Human
Whaley 2020	Recommendations for the conduct of systematic reviews in toxicology and environmental health research (COSTER)	1	Lancaster Environment Centre, Lancaster University	Europe	Lancaster University Faculty of Science and Technology and Lancaster Environment Centre, UK Economic & Social Research Council (ESRC) “Radical Futures” programme, Engineering & Physical Science Research Council (EPSRC) “Impact Acceleration Award” EP/K50421X/1	Toxicology and environmental health	Human, non-human and in vitro
WHO 2019	International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) Monographs on the Identification of Carcinogenic Hazards to Humans: Preamble	1	World Health Organization (WHO)	Europe	Not specified	Carcinogenic hazards	Human and non-human (animal data)
Wong 2013	Realist And MEta-narrative Evidence Syntheses: Evolving Standards (RAMESES) publication standards: meta-	1	Queen Mary University of London, UK	Europe	NIH Research Health Services and Delivery Research Programme (NIHR HS&DR)	Complex, multi-disciplinary interventions	Human

Framework ID	Title	Version	Developing Organization or Developer Affiliation	Location	Funding Source	Topic Area	Evidence Type
	narrative reviews						
Woodruff 2014	The Navigation Guide Systematic Review Methodology	1	Program on Reproductive Health and the Environment (PRHE), University of California, San Diego (UCSD)	USA	Clarence Heller, Passport, Forsythia, Johnson Family, Fred Gellert, and Rose Foundations, Heinz Endowments, Kaiser Permanente, NY Community Trust, Philip R. Lee Institute for Health Policy Studies, Planned Parenthood Federation of America, NIEHS, and EPA	Environmental health	Human and non-human (animal data)

Table 3. Summary of systematic review domains addressed by each framework

Framework ID	Framework Name	Addressed by PRISMA 2020									Unique to EH
		Research Question	Protocol	Search Strategy	Study Selection	Data Extraction	Data Synthesis	Risk of Bias Assessment	Overall Certainty Assessment	Reporting Results	Integration of Non-Human Research
CEE 2022	CEE	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
EFSA 2010	EFSA	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y
EPA 2022	IRIS	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Farhat 2022	[Not specified]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
OHAT 2019	OHAT	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Page 2021	PRISMA 2020	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
Schaefer 2017	TCEQ	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y
Shaffril 2020	GuFSyADD	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
Vandenberg 2016	SYRINA	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	Y
Welch 2015	PRISMA-E	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N
Whaley 2020	COSTER	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
WHO 2019	IARC	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Wong 2013	RAMESES	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
Woodruff 2014	Navigation Guide	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y

TOTAL	13	13	14	14	11	13	13	13	12		10
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Table 4. Summary of framework guidance within each domain

Domain	Themes	Framework References
Research Question	A specific and answerable research question should be stated in the systematic review	EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Schaefer 2017, Shaffril 2020, Vandenberg 2016, Welch 2015, Whaley 2020, Wong 2013, Woodruff 2014
	Research questions should be formulated using the PICO or PECO (Population, Intervention/Exposure, Comparison, Outcome) format	EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Schaefer 2017, Shaffril 2020, Vandenberg 2016, Welch 2015, Whaley 2020, Woodruff 2014
Protocol	Systematic reviews should be conducted following a prespecified protocol	EFSA 2010, CEE 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Schaefer 2017, Shaffril 2020, Vandenberg 2016, Welch 2015, Whaley 2020, Wong 2013, Woodruff 2014
	Review protocols should be publicly available	EFSA 2010, CEE 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Vandenberg 2016, Welch 2015, Whaley 2020
Search Strategy	Search strategies should be created to identify all relevant information with consideration of appropriate terms and well-defined limitations	EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, CEE 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Schaefer 2017, Shaffril 2020, Vandenberg 2016, Welch 2015, Whaley 2020, WHO 2019, Wong 2013, Woodruff 2014
Study Selection	Potentially relevant studies should be screened based on well-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria (eligibility criteria)	OHAT 2019, Welch 2015, Whaley 2020, WHO 2019, Wong 2013, Woodruff 2014
	Screening should be performed by two or more reviewers	CEE 2022, EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, Page 2021, Schaefer 2017, Shaffril 2020, Vandenberg 2015

Domain	Themes	Framework References
Data Extraction	Characteristics of eligible studies should be collected in detail	EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Schaefer 2017, Shaffril 2020, Wong 2013, Woodruff 2014
	Data extraction should be performed by two or more reviewers (duplicate extraction or extraction with review by a second researcher)	CEE 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Whaley 2020
Data Synthesis Methods	Quantitative and qualitative methods may be used for data synthesis	CEE 2022, EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Shaffril 2020, Vandenberg 2016, Welch 2015, Whaley 2020, WHO 2019, Wong 2013
Risk of Bias Assessment	Studies that meet the inclusion criteria should be critically evaluated for risk of bias using various tools depending on the type of study design and populations being assessed	CEE 2022, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Shaffril 2020, Schaefer 2017, Vandenberg 2016, Whaley 2020, WHO 2019, Woodruff 2019, Wong 2013
Certainty Assessment	Certainty of evidence may be assessed using the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) approach	Farhat 2022, Page 2021, Whaley 2020
	Certainty of evidence may be assessed using a modified version of the GRADE approach	EPA 2022, OHAT 2019, Vandenberg 2016, Welch 2015, Woodruff 2014
	Certainty of evidence may be assessed using a tool created by Beck et al. (2015) that deconstructs toxicity development into elements	Schaefer 2017
	Certainty of evidence may be assessed using Bradford Hill Criteria	WHO 2019
	Certainty of evidence may be assessed using an approach selected at the discretion of the author	CEE 2022, EFSA 2010, Wong 2013
Reporting Results	Results can be reported as monographs, meeting reports, and/or peer-reviewed journal publications	EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, OHAT 2019, Whaley 2020, Wong 2013, Woodruff 2019
	Specific standards for reporting are recommended	CEE 2022, Farhat 2022, Page 2020, Shaffril 2020, Welch 2015, WHO 2019

Table 5. Approaches to operationalizing framework domains

Subdomain	Detailed Findings
Research Question	
Who's involved in formulating the research question?	Research and/or review team (CEE 2022, EPA 2022, OHAT 2019)
	Subject matter experts (CEE 2022, EPA 2022, Vandenberg 2016, Wong 2013)
	Multidisciplinary team (Woodruff 2014)
	Evaluation team (OHAT 2019)
	Funders (Wong 2013)
	End users (Wong 2013)
Guidance for integrating evidence on non-human exposures	Separate PECO question for each evidence stream: non-animal, laboratory animal, wildlife (epidemiology), and human (epidemiology) (Vandenberg 2016)
Protocol Development	
Who's involved in protocol development?	Research and/or review team, commissioners, subject matter experts (CEE 2022, OHAT 2019, EFSA 2010)
	Evaluation team and technical advisors (OHAT 2019)
	Relevant stakeholders (EFSA 2010)
	Interdisciplinary team (Woodruff 2014)
	Feedback from the public (OHAT 2019)
Approaches to protocol development	Cochrane (EFSA 2010, Whaley 2020)
	PROCEED standards (CEE 2022, EFSA 2010)
	PRISMA-P (Farhat 2022, Page 2021)
	Document and disclose any changes to the protocol in a transparent manner (Vandenberg 2016)
	Peer review (CEE 2022, Whaley 2020, EFSA 2010)

Subdomain	Detailed Findings
Approaches to protocol review	Public comment (EPA 2022, Whaley 2020)
Approaches to publication or public posting of the protocol	PROSPERO (Farhat 2022, Whaley 2020, Page 2021, Vandenberg 2016)
	PROCEED (CEE 2022)
	CAMARADES (Farhat 2022)
	Zenodo (Whaley 2020)
	Center of Open Science (Whaley 2020)
	Developer website (OHAT 2019, EPA 2022)
	Any reputable repository (EFSA 2010)
Search Strategy	
Who's involved in developing the search strategy?	Research and/or review team (Woodruff 2014, EFSA 2010, OHAT 2019, Wong 2013, CEE 2022, WHO 2019, Vandenberg 2016, EPA 2022)
	Librarian and/or information specialist (CEE 2022, WHO 2019, Vandenberg 2016, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022)
	Subject matter experts (EPA 2022)
	Other relevant stakeholders (OHAT 2019, Wong 2013)
Research databases	The following databases may be considered for SRs on environmental health topics: PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, Embase, Toxline, Google Scholar, Dimensions.ai, ACM Digital Library, BASE, ClinicalTrials.gov
	SYRCLE guide to identifying relevant animal studies (Farhat 2022)
Approaches to unpublished evidence	Gray literature search should be considered (Woodruff 2014, OHAT 2019, CEE 2022, EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, Whaley 2020, Vandenberg 2016, Welch 2015, Page 2021, WHO 2019)

Subdomain	Detailed Findings
Approaches to restricting the search	Describe and report any search restrictions (e.g., human research only, language, date) (Woodruff 2014, CEE 2022, Page 2021, Shaffril 2020)
	Restrictions may be guided and justified according to scope of the research question (EPA 2022, Schaefer 2017, Whaley 2020)
Study Selection	
Approaches to formulating eligibility criteria	The eligibility criteria should reflect the elements of the research question (CEE 2022, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, Schaefer 2017)
	Document eligibility criteria (Page 2021, Schaefer 2017, Whaley 2020, WHO 2019, Wong 2013)
Who's involved in study selection?	Research and/or review team (2 reviewers) without AI support (CEE 2022, EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Schaefer 2017, Shaffril 2020, Whaley 2020, WHO 2019, Woodruff 2014)
	Research and/or review team (2 reviewers) with AI support (EPA 2022, Vandenberg 2016)
Documentation of study selection	Document the number of sources included in the review with reasons for exclusion at each stage (Page 2021, Wong 2013)
	Document reasons for exclusion of potentially eligible studies based on pre specified criteria (Page 2021)
Software for study selection	Mentioned specific softwares for study selection (EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Schaefer 2017, Vandenberg 2016)
Approaches to reaching consensus	Consultation among team, generally with involvement of a third reviewer (CEE 2022, EFSA 2010, EPA2022, Farhat 2022, Page 2021, Vandenberg 2016, Whaley 2020)
Data Extraction	
Who's involved in data extraction?	Research and/or review team (2 reviewers) without AI support (CEE 2022, EFSA 2010, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Whaley 2020)
	Research and/or review team (2 reviewers) with AI support (EPA 2022)
Software for data extraction	Recommend software to facilitate extraction (EPA 2022, CEE 2022)

Subdomain	Detailed Findings
Approaches to reaching consensus	Usually by a third person that could be a team member or a technical advisor (CEE 2022, EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Whaley 2020)
<i>Data Synthesis</i>	
Approaches to data synthesis	Methods for quantitative synthesis include: statistical aggregation, assessment of heterogeneity, calculation of pooled effect measures, meta-regression, and sub-group analysis (CEE 2022, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Whaley 2020, WHO 2019, Wong 2013)
	Methods for qualitative synthesis include: thematic analysis, narrative summary, meta-study, Miles and Huberman’s cross-case techniques, realist synthesis, content analysis, case survey, and qualitative comparative analysis method, qualitative aggregation, paradigm bridging (seeking commonalities in underlying conceptual and theoretical assumptions), paradigm bracketing (highlighting differences in these assumptions), interplay (exploring tensions), and meta-theorizing (exploring patterns that span conflicting understandings) (Shaffril 2020, Wong 2013)
Software use for data synthesis	Specific software suggested to facilitate analysis (Farhat 2022)
Guidance for integrating evidence on non-human exposures	Human, animal, and/or mechanistic evidence streams may be integrated during data synthesis (EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Schaefer 2017, Woodruff 2014)
<i>Study-level Appraisal</i>	
Approaches to risk of bias assessment for randomized studies	For randomized trials, including randomized wildlife populations, the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool, and OHAT RoB Tool are recommended. (EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Shaffril 2020, Schaefer 2017, Vandenberg 2016, Woodruff 2019)
Approaches to risk of bias assessment for non-randomized studies	For non-randomized trials, including wildlife populations, ROBINS-I, Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS), Downs and Black, OHAT RoB Tool, and NIEHS Office of the Report on Carcinogens (ORoC) Tool are recommended (EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Shaffril 2020, Schaefer 2017, Vandenberg 2016, Woodruff 2019)
Other approaches to risk of bias assessment	Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (CEE) Critical Appraisal Tool for randomized and non-randomized trials (CEE 2022)
	Mixed Method Appraisal Tool (MMAT) mixed-methods research design (Wong 2013)

Subdomain	Detailed Findings
	Critical Skill Appraisal Programme (CASP) for qualitative research design (Wong 2013)
Who's involved in the risk of bias assessment?	Research and/or review team (CEE 2022, EFSA 2010, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021, Shaffril 2020, Whaley 2020, Wong 2013, Woodruff 2014)
	Subject matter experts (Shaffril 2020, WHO 2019)
Process for reaching consensus	Selection of most conservative judgment (OHAT 2019)
	Discussion with a third person (Farhat 2022)
	Inter-rater agreement can be quantified using Cohen's Kappa analysis (two reviewers) or Fleiss Kappa analysis (no limit on the number of reviewers) (Shaffril 2020)
Guidance for integrating evidence on non-human exposures	Separate risk of bias and/or certainty assessment of multiple evidence streams including both human and non-human data (EFSA 2010, EPA 2022, Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Schaefer 2017, Woodruff 2014)
	Klimisch method and Good Laboratory Practices (GLP) for in vivo studies
	SAR models and OECD for in silico studies
	REFLECT-LFS/Reporting Guidelines for Randomized Controlled Trials in Livestock and Food Safety (EFSA 2010)
Overall Certainty Assessment	
Approaches to overall certainty assessment	GRADE: risk of bias, inconsistency (heterogeneity), indirectness, imprecision, publication bias, magnitude of effect, dose-response gradient, and opposing residual confounding (Farhat 2022, Page 2021, Whaley 2020, Woodruff 2014)
	Modified GRADE: risk of bias, unexplained inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, publication bias, magnitude of effect, dose response, residual confounding, consistency (OHAT 2019)
	Modified GRADE: confidence, consistency, dose-response gradient, magnitude of effect, coherence (EPA 2022)
	Beck et al. (2015) assessment tool: type of data, study design, study quality, sample size, human relevance, and risk of bias (Schaefer 2017)

Subdomain	Detailed Findings
	Quality/reliability of the included studies, relevance/external validity of the included studies, size and statistical significance of the observed effects, consistency of the effects across studies or sites and the extent to which this can be explained by other variables (effect modifiers), clarity of the relationship between the intensity of the intervention and the outcome, existence of any indirect evidence that supports or refutes the inference, lack of other plausible competing explanations of the observed effects (bias or confounding) (CEE 2022)
Approaches to assessment of publication bias	GRADE: “undetected” or “strongly suspected” (OHAT 2019, Vandenberg 2016)
	Exploratory plots and tests (e.g., funnel plot) (CEE 2022)
	Compare outcomes and analyzes pre-specified in study registers, protocols, and statistical analysis plans with results that were available in study reports; contour enhanced funnel plots, Egger’s test (Page 2021)
Terminology for describing overall certainty in the evidence	Known to be toxic, probably toxic, possibly toxic, not classifiable, probably not toxic (Woodruff 2014)
	High, moderate/medium, low, very low (Farhat 2022, OHAT 2019, Page 2021)
	Five levels of certainty: robust, moderate, slight, indeterminate, compelling evidence of no effect (EPA 2022)
	High, medium, low (Schaefer 2017, Vandenberg 2016)
	Sufficient evidence of carcinogenicity, Limited evidence of carcinogenicity, Inadequate evidence regarding carcinogenicity, Evidence suggesting lack of carcinogenicity; The agent is carcinogenic to humans (Group 1), The agent is probably carcinogenic to humans (Group 2A), The agent is possibly carcinogenic to humans (Group 2B), The agent is not classifiable as to its carcinogenicity to humans (Group 3) (WHO 2019)
Guidance for integrating evidence on non-human exposures	Separate certainty assessment for separate streams of evidence: evidence of cancer in humans, evidence of cancer in experimental animals, mechanistic evidence: risk of bias, estimate (magnitude) of effect, precision (number of studies), risk of bias (quality of study), consistency, temporality, dose response gradient, coherence, specificity (generalizability) (WHO 2019)
	Analysis of the strength of association between exposure and adverse effect within evidence streams Analysis of the strength of association between the chemical and endocrine disrupting activity within streams - Limitations in methodological quality of the research in the stream (including risk of bias) - Inconsistency

Subdomain	Detailed Findings
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Imprecision - Large magnitude of effect - Dose response gradients - Confounding is minimized (Vandenberg 2016)
Reporting findings	
Elements to reported or presented	Tables and graphics of the findings (EPA 2022, OHAT 2019)
	Detailed characteristics of individual studies (OHAT 2019)
	ROSES format (CEE 2022, Shaffril 2020)
	SYRCLE gold standard publication checklist (Farhat 2022)
	Study characteristics, data collected, results, meta-analysis (EFSA 2010, Wong 2013)
	Flow diagram of study selection, search strategy, coding/extraction form, appraisal method (Shaffril 2020)
	Exposure characterization, overall strengths and limitations (humans and animals), mechanistic evidence (WHO 2019)
	Research question, applicability, justification of search limitations, search terms, PICO question, analysis/synthesis approach, individual study results, results of synthesis or meta-analysis, certainty of evidence, discussion of limitations and implications of the results for practice and policy (Page 2021, Welch 2015)
Making the report public	Organizational website (OHAT 2019)
	ROSES guidelines, PRISMA standards, or RAMESES guidelines for reporting are recommended (CEE 2022, Farhat 2022, Page 2020, Shaffril 2020, Wong 2013)
	Essential elements that must be reported include: exposure characterization; cancer in humans (results of epidemiological studies pertinent to an evaluation of carcinogenicity in humans are summarized. The overall strengths and limitations of the epidemiological evidence base are highlighted to indicate how the evaluation was reached.); cancer in experimental animals (results pertinent to an evaluation of carcinogenicity in experimental animals are summarized to indicate how the evaluation was reached.); mechanistic evidence (results pertinent to an evaluation of the mechanistic evidence on

Subdomain	Detailed Findings
	carcinogenicity are summarized to indicate how the evaluation was reached.) (WHO 2019)

Table 6. Systematic review feasibility considerations described by framework developers

Framework	Funding	COI	Personnel	Other Considerations	Limitations
CEE 2022	Disclosed within the protocol	Disclosed within protocol	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified
EFSA 2010	Requirement of funding disclosure and process of disclosing funding is not specified	Disclosed within protocol	Not specified	Criteria for prioritizing questions to be answered by a systematic review: prioritization of model parameters for which refinement of the parameter estimates is considered most critical (e.g. in risk assessment), assessment of the quantity and quality of available evidence, the source and potential confidentiality of the evidence, the need for transparency and/or for integrating conflicting results, and the resources needed for carrying out the review.	Not specified
EPA 2022	Disclosed through the data extraction software (HAWC)	Disclosed through the data extraction software (HAWC)	Not specified	Structured, reproducible procedures for aspects of IRIS assessments that are outside the usual domain of systematic review: evaluating mechanistic data and hypotheses, modeling pharmacokinetics and exposure-response relationships, and deriving toxicity values.	Not specified
Farhat 2022	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	Replacement of animal studies may be achieved in part by using systematic reviews to summarize findings from the application of new approach methodologies (NAMs) and provide validation for these new approaches.	Not specified

Framework	Funding	COI	Personnel	Other Considerations	Limitations
OHAT 2019	Sources of support section in handbook protocol	Potential technical advisors screened for COI prior to service	Not specified	Review team members should have at least a Master's degree or equivalent in epidemiology, toxicology, environmental health sciences, or related field; experience in evaluating occupational or environmental studies is preferred.	Not specified
Page 2021	Disclosure in a specific funding section of the systematic review	Disclosure should be done using the format requested by the publishing entity	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified

Framework	Funding	COI	Personnel	Other Considerations	Limitations
Schaefer 2017	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	<p>1. Problem Formulation and Protocol Development: In this framework, the problem formulation and the protocol development sections are presented in a general manner because they must be applicable to a wide array of chemicals, data sets, and endpoints.</p> <p>2. Literature Searches: While initial search terms may limit the identification of relevant literature, the review of additional sources (e.g., toxicological reviews) allows for identification of other relevant literature for inclusion and the refinement of search criteria.</p> <p>3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Defining one set of inclusion and exclusion criteria for all chemicals is difficult since often the criteria will be chemical and/or purpose-specific.</p> <p>4. Scoring Criteria: Defining a distinct set of rules across the different types of studies and data streams can be difficult. These criteria may be revised as needed to better assess the available data depending on the chemical under assessment. In addition, the study quality criteria provided are general and subject to scientific judgment and interpretation.</p>

Framework	Funding	COI	Personnel	Other Considerations	Limitations
Shaffril 2020	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified
Vandenberg 2016	Not specified	Disclosure through a conflict of interest statement in the review	Not specified	<p>Review questions should be selected that are feasible, tractable, of high priority, not duplicative, and have a high potential to impact decision-making (considering the time and effort required to conduct a systematic review)</p> <p>Completion of an SR could take more than a year to conduct if a relatively large dataset is identified; balance with processes for regulatory decision-making and other public health oriented actions.</p>	Short-term needs: development of methods for evaluation in vitro and in silico data, case study shedding light on important procedural issues, including the number and types of experts needed to evaluate evidence from different scientific fields
Welch 2015	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	Certain terminology used in the reporting guideline may not be well defined or widely used and may be defined differently by different users.
Whaley 2020	Not specified	Disclosure through a conflict of interest statement in	Not specified	Not specified	The consensus process when developing COSTER may be lacking

Framework	Funding	COI	Personnel	Other Considerations	Limitations
		the review			
WHO 2019	Not specified	Disclosure through the WHO Declaration of Interests Form	Not specified	Not specified	Options to prevent cancer vary from one situation to another and 10 across geographical regions and take many factors into account, including different national priorities. Therefore, no recommendations are given in the Monographs with regard to regulation, legislation, or other policy approaches, which are the responsibility of individual governments or organizations.
Wong 2013	Disclosure in a specific funding section in the review	Disclosure through a conflict of interest statement in the review	Not specified	Not specified	This publication standard is not a detailed guide of how to undertake a meta-narrative review. Other resources, both published (see Introduction section) and in preparation, are better suited for this purpose. These standards have been developed as a guide to assist the quality of reporting of meta-narrative reviews and the work of publishers, editors, and reviewers.
Woodruff 2014	Not specified	Disclosed in conflict of interest domain	Not specified; 9 scientists involved in the case study.	Not specified	Application can be poorly executed